

Essential requirements for ecological and economic machining of steel

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Abstract

Dry processing within metal-cutting manufacture needs to be applied in order to reduce the adverse effects of cooling lubricants on the environment. In a study by Schäpermeier, the author indicates that during machining above a fixed temperature value, the contact area between the underside of the chip and the rake face (chip underside/rake face) experience boundary friction. As this process generates lubricants that are not harmful to the environment, the basic requirement for dry processing during chip formation with boundary friction is fulfilled.

In addition, the production of lubricants reduces the wear rate of the tool and eventually creates an economic incentive to achieve dry processing, by selecting the specifications to allow for boundary friction during the process of machining.

During the machine processing the highest temperatures occur in the contact area chip underside/rake face. In contrast to the assumption of FE modelling, the chip underside and the rake face are not smooth, but show a microscopic roughness. As a result, only parts of the contact area experience friction. This roughness on both surfaces leads to the formation of “cavities” that can be filled with cooling lubricants at low temperatures, and hence affects chip formation. With increasing temperature, the protrusions of the chip underside “soften” and the cavities’ volume decreases. Following that, the protrusions are welded onto the rake face and form built-up edges. Eventually the temperature of the protrusions reaches the melting temperature of steel and the cavities are filled, thus the requirements for boundary friction are met. In this case only the protrusions of the rake face are in contact with the chip underside and the chip can transmit normal and transverse forces. The main characteristic of this process is that the total area of the protrusions represents the size of the machining surface. In spite of the melting temperatures, the protrusions at the chip underside do not melt due to the significantly short residence time and remain on the chip when it exits the contact area.

It is therefore crucial to achieve the required temperature within the contact area to allow for a machining process with boundary friction. This temperature range is solely dependent on the dimensions of the machining surfaces of both the work piece and the tool, as well as the cutting speed. The dimensions generally differ between roughing and finishing and further depend on the magnitude of the speed ratio. Merely the specifications of the feed and cutting speed determine whether the machining process can be achieved in an economically and ecologically advantageous way.

Keywords: Similarity mechanics, thermal speed ratio, boundary friction, inherent lubricant, dry machining, stability, cutting data control calculator.

Short biography

Studied mechanical engineering at the Duisburg Engineering School. Degree in engineering with university entrance qualification. Studied heat, power and work machines, RWTH Aachen. Degree Dipl.-Ing.. Practice, Head of Physics in contract research at the Battelle Institute Ffm. Promotion to Dr.-Ing. at the University of Karlsruhe. 1985 Lateral entry into machining, self-employment.

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